

Impact of Personality Traits on Business Students' Learning Approaches

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 25, 2021

Accepted:
November 31, 2021

Keywords :

Personality,
Neuroticism, Big Five
Inventory, structure
education, Private Sector

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5812275

Abstract

The present study examined that how big five personality dimensions are associated with student approaches to learning. Two hundred (86 female and 114 male) business students from public and private sector universities of KPK (Pakistan) participated in the study. The participants responded to the Big Five Inventory-44 (BFI-44) of personality and RASI (Revised Approaches of Studying Inventory) for students learning approaches. Using Pearson correlation, stepwise regression procedures and structure education, it was found that the big five personality dimensions are associated with learning approaches and also have impact on learning approaches. Results showed that four personality dimension i.e. extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience have positive correlation with deep, surface, strategic learning approaches. One dimension neuroticism did not significantly correlated with surface approach, while has positive and significant relation with remaining two approaches i.e. deep and strategic. The study also found that all personality dimensions have impact on deep learning approach. Openness to experience is the only dimension that did not impact the surface approach while rests have impact. Neuroticism has no impact on strategic approach while other four dimensions have impact on strategic approach. Managerial implications, limitations and future directions are also discussed.

Introduction

Students' approaches towards learning are of great importance in their academic pursuit. Due to its significance this phenomenon is being researched since long (Duff et al., 2004). The pursuit for analysis of learning approaches started by Marton & Saljo, (1976) is still in progress. Educationists, psychologists and researchers of organizational behavior are equally interested in studying the learning approaches of the students. Various factors influence the learning approaches (Duff et al., 2004). Those include the information processing style (Messick, 1984), personality traits (Bustao et al., 1999; Zhang, 2003; Premuzic et al., 2007; Shokri et al., 2007; Premuzic and Furnham, 2009; Premuzic, Furnham and Lewis, 2006) demographics like age and prior education (Duff, 1999; Richardson, 1995) and gender (Wilson, Smart and Watson, 1996).

As Tokar (1995) stated that the five-factor model (for detail see next paragraph) is one of the most prominent model of personality structure. Many scholars (for example, Goldberg, 1993; Taylor & MacDonald, 1999) have argued that the big five personality traits model explained for a large amount of the variability in personality. Costa & McCrae (1992) big five personality dimensions include neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experiences, agreeableness and conscientiousness the first dimension is neuroticism, which is characterized as "the propensity for individuals to experience negative emotions in response to adverse conditions such as frustrations, losses, or the prospect of frustrations or losses".

People are high on this scale tend to experience such negative feelings as emotional instability, shame, guilt, distrust, and low self-esteem. The second dimension is extraversion, which is characterized as extraversion is "the act, state, or habit of being predominantly concerned with and obtaining gratification from what is outside the self". People scoring high on the extraversion tend to be social and assertive. They feel easy to work with people. The third dimension openness to experience, which is as characterized by such attributes as broad-mindedness, active imagination, preference for variety and freedom of judgment. Also, people who are high on this tend to be less conservative and conventional.

The fourth dimension is agreeableness, which is as people high on the agreeableness scale are fundamentally unselfish, sympathetic, and readily helpful. Also, they value and respect other people's beliefs and traditional. The fifth dimension is conscientiousness, which is as individuals who are high on the Conscientiousness scale is characterized as being purposeful, responsible, strong-willed and trustworthy (Costa and McCrae, 1992). The five-factor model has attracted the attention of many personality psychologists. The work of Costa and McCrae (1985, 1992) is one of the most noteworthy. Because first time they related personality model with education.

There are three students learning approaches (Duff et al., 2004). Those include deep, surface and strategic approaches. The students with a deep approach want to find out the deeper meaning in the text. They

are critical, logical and relate what they learn to their previous knowledge (Baeten, M. K., 2010). Their motivation is intrinsic and they look for a personal comprehension independent of the syllabus (Entwistle, 1988). Students tend to develop a deeper approach to their studies over the course of time (Entwistle&Ramsden 1983; Svensson, 1977).

The students with a surface approach concentrate on memorizing without any strain to find a deeper meaning or understanding of the material. They are most concerned about passing the exams and are not really interested in the topic itself (Entwistle&Tait, 1996). Their motivation is extrinsic and they take on a syllabus-bound approach to studying (Entwistle, 1988). Students who use the strategic approach are efficient at organizing their work, managing their time and work hard in their studies. They care about their working conditions and have clear goals for their studies (Entwistle and Tait, 1996). The students with a strategic approach aim at achieving the highest possible marks (Entwistle and Ramsden, 1983).

It is important to consider learning approaches of the business students who are most likely future executives. Student's abilities, skills and learning during their academic training are likely to enhance their organization performance in future. As it has been stated above, there are various factors that affect the students' learning, but the impact of personality on learning approaches is relatively less studied as suggested by Duff et al, (2004). Study emphasized on more research on the relationship of personality dimension and learning approaches using different methods, and settings.

Therefore, this study will analyze the impact of personality dimension namely extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness (Costa and McCrae (1992) on the learning approaches namely, strategic, deep and surface approaches of learning (Marton&Saljo, 1976). Although studies exist in literature on this subject about students studying in various academic disciplines, but no study has been conducted on learning approaches of the students in Pakistan, especially in the business discipline (management sciences).

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In the developed world many studies are carried out to see the impact of many factors (for example thinking styles, cultural value, personality dimension and learning context and environment and many more). But there is a dearth of such studies in the developing countries. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the impact of personality on student learning approaches.

In the study, business students are chosen because, after completion of their studies they have to enter in the corporate world and will lead the organization. Therefore, it is prime concern to study these approaches to facilitate students learning during their education and later on their professional life.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Approaches to learning

Work considering ways in which students approach learning has been of interest to educational researchers for over 30 years. The seminal work of Marton and Saljo (1976) identified student learning could be categorized into two general strategies: deep processing and surface processing. Applying these concepts, researchers in various locations, have extended Marton and Saljo's effort to develop models and inventories which purport to measure students' approaches to learning (SAL). Although subtle differences exist between these models, they all recognize three fundamental approaches to learning. These defining approaches to learning are labeled as deep approach, surface approach and strategic approach. An individual adopting a deep approach is said to look for meaning in the matter being studied and relates those ideas to other experiences and ideas with a critical approach. A surface approach reflects a reliance on rote-learning and memorization in isolation to other ideas. A third defining approach, labeled a strategic approach, is associated with an emphasis on organization, study skills, and a desire to achieve the highest grades.

2.2 Modeling approaches to learning

Traditional predictive models of academic performance focus on the importance of variables such as intelligence and motivation. Personality is often included as a predictor alongside these variables (see Furnham, 1995 for a review). However, educational psychologists from the SAL school see learning as contextually-based and bottom-up and criticise traditional theoretical models, as being top-down and acontextual. SAL researchers claim their instruments are based on a theoretical rationale grounded in how students actually go about learning tasks in educational settings, for example, classrooms and lecture halls (Watkins, 1998). Ramsden (1992) suggests students learning outcomes are directly influenced by their orientation to learning. An individual orientation to learning is likely to be influenced by their prior educational experiences. Their approach to learning is a function of both their learning orientation and their perceptions of the task requirements.

Learning task perceptions are in turn influenced by the context of learning (curriculum, teaching processes and assessment methods). A deep approach is likely to be encouraged where: the learning task is

perceived to be relevant to students' interests (Fransson, 1977); the instructor is supportive and demonstrates interest and enthusiasm (Ramsden, 1979); and students are provided with the opportunity to manage their own learning (Ramsden and Entwistle, 1981). By contrast, a surface approach is more likely to occur when assessment methods reward reproducing information (Dart & Clarke, 1991); excessive anxiety (Fransson, 1977); or a heavy workload (Ramsden, 1992). A strategic approach is characterized by a highly organized approach to study and high achievement motivation (Watkins, 1982).

2.3 Approaches to learning instruments

A number of instruments have been developed to measure students' approaches to learning, including: Biggs' (1987) Study Processes Questionnaire, developed in Australia; Schmeck, Ribich, and Ramaniah (1977) creation of the Inventory of Learning Processes in the United States; in the Netherlands, Vermunt's (1994) Inventory of Learning Styles (ILS); and in the UK, the Approaches to Studying Inventory (ASI) (Entwistle, Hanley, & Hounsell, 1979). Since its development in the 1970s, the ASI (Entwistle et al., 1979) has been one of the most widely used questionnaires considering student learning in higher education (HE) settings in the UK. Reflecting relatively recent changes in higher education (e.g. mass higher education, significantly reduced per capita funding, reduction in student grants and the imposition of fees), the ASI was revised several times during the mid-1990s to create the Revised Approaches to Studying Inventory (RASI), measuring three constructs of deep approach, surface approach and strategic approach. A 30-item short-form version of the RASI has been shown to yield scores with satisfactory psychometric properties (Duff, 1997, 1999, 2002, 2003) and takes around 10–15 minutes to administer five-factor model (e.g. Costa & McCrae, 1992, 1995; Furnham, 1996, but see Block (1995) for a more critical perspective). The so-called Big Five factors are usually labeled extraversion, neuroticism, openness to experience, agreeableness and conscientiousness.

2.4 Personality, Approach to Studying

This section discussed that how personality dimension influence students approaching to learning. It is not enough to concentrate merely on the intellectual aspect of learning behavior. A complete picture of the individual's learning it is also important to consider emotional aspects (Miller, 1991). Competence is not the only decisive thing in a learning situation. Personality affects the rate and the way in which people learn and the way they can handle changes (Revelle, 1995). Not only do personality traits influence the way students deal with their study task, personality traits likewise have an effect on the actual knowledge creation of the students. Personality and learning style are different representations of the same underlying structure (Messick, 1994; Riding, Burton, Rees & Sharratt, 1995).

There are many factors which influence learning style but personality is certainly one of them, which suggests a fairly stable base for learning styles (Adema, 2000). Personality is likely to form a boundary for the learning style which may then be adapted to situational demands. Approaches to studying can be described as a combination of temperament and effort (Schouwenburg & Kossowska, 1999). Psychological styles are not fixed traits but stable patterns which arise from transaction between the individual and his/her environment (Kolb, 1984, pp. 95-98).

Learning styles seem to be modifiable, but not without limits (Adema, 2000). Basic personality traits remain the same while motivational states are dependent on the situation. Personality does not specifically determine actions, but rather attitudes towards behavior (Vermetten, Lodewijks & Vermunt, 2001). Personality traits can in this sense serve as either directors or blocks for learning strategies (Blickle, 1996) intervened by motivation (De Raad & Schouwenburg, 1996; Rayner & Riding, 1997).

3. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

To achieve its objective, study was completed in two phases. In phase one pilot study was conducted to check the reliability of the instruments used and to find out that is there any need for change(s) in the instruments or not? The main study was carried in second phase. This chapter presents the research methodology adopted for investigation of the relationship among personality traits students approaches to learning.

3.1 Population

The data collection instrument was "questionnaire" while a sample of 300 business students were collected from public and private sector universities of KPK to see diverse patterns of learning approaches at higher level among different business students. Sample is drawn in two stages in first stage using simple random sampling to select four universities out of 26 universities of KPK. Then using convenient sampling to select three hundred business students from public and private sectors universities. The selected universities are Institute of

Management Sciences Peshawar, University of Peshawar (IM Study), Quartaba University, Peshawar and Northern University Nowshera.

3.2 Sampling

Sample is drawn in two stages. In first stage using simple random sampling to select four universities out of 26 universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. In second stage using convenient sampling were select three hundred business students from two public and two private sector universities of KPK. Sample of the main study is drawn from four universities. In the main study, 300 questionnaires were distributed in public and private sector universities of KPK in which 200 were returned (response rate of 66.67%). The participants in this study were business students of public sector and private sector university of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) and participants were enrolled in BBA, MBA, MS/MBA (3.5) and PhD in last semester of their course. In this study questionnaire is adopted as data collection tool. For this study respondent are selected from public sector universities such as (Institute of Management Studies Peshawar, University of Peshawar) while in private sector universities (Quartaba University, Peshawar and Northern University, Nowshera). The data was entered in Ms Excel 2007- worksheet. It was arranged in desired manner and was then imported in SPSS 21 file. Necessary coding was done.

3.3 Questionnaire

Questionnaire of this study was comprised of three sections along with a covering page which describes the basic purpose of introduction the study. First section was demographics. In second section three were questions about personality trait and third section items about students' approaches to learning. Questionnaire has been adopted from the work of Andreou, Vlachose&Androueo; 2006, Duff 2003 and their instrument details are discussed below.

Table 1: Data collection instrument and analysis

3.3.1 Student Approach to Learning

Name of variable	Sources of instruments	No of items
RASI(Revised approach of studying inventory)	Duff et al 2004	30
Big Five Inventory-44 (BFI-44) of personality	John & Srivastava (1999)	44

For this study revised approach of studying inventory (RASI) (duff, 2003) is used. RASI has 30 items with likert scale from 1 to 5 (1 for strongly Disagree and 5 for strongly Agree) measuring three distinct learning approaches. The instrument has 10 items to measure Deep approach, 10 items for surface approach and 10 items for strategic approach.

3.4 Procedures

Heads of the departments of management sciences of different universities were approached. They were briefed about the study and permission was taken from them in written form. The total 300 questionnaires were distributed personally. The respondents were also briefed about the study of and its objectives. They were also ensured and that the data will be used the confidentially of the data will be ensured and that the data will be used only for research purpose. The questionnaires were collect after one day so that respondent filled the questionnaire with ease. They were also asked their feedback that's was the questionnaire was easy to understand and comprehend or not? If which item need to changes/corrections. The gathered the data were entered in excel sheet than transfer to SPSS file. And feedbacks of pilot study were also recorded in Ms World documents. A code book was developed for the ease in analysis. After coding, variable were defined, calculated and coded as per the code book.

3.5 Result and Conclusion of the Pilot Study

To meet the two objective of the pilot study were obtained by analysis of the questionnaires data and feedback of the respondents. First the reliability of the instrument was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha coefficient of reliability (Cronbach, 1951). According to George & Mallery (2003), the value of Cronbach in the range $0.8 > \alpha > 0.7$ is desirable and show that instrument is internally consistent and is reliable for measuring the concepts. A factor analysis (varimax rotation) was done for 74 items of four variables. The values of Exploratory Factor Analysis for 74 items shows that the minimum factor loading value ranges from 0.52 to maximum value of 0.91, indicating that all 74 items have met the acceptable standard of validity. Apart from this the results of Kaiser Meyer Olkin Test of measuring sampling adequacy indicated that it was acceptable. As values within ranges of 0.70 to 0.90 are generally acceptable (Kaiser, 1974). Following are the α value of the variables used in the pilot study:

Table No. 2: Reliability Test

Instrument/ Variable	No. of item	Factor Loading	KMO Test	Cronbach Alpha
Deep Approach	10	0.52-.81	0.91	0.86
Surface Approach	10	0.64-.38	0.87	0.78
Strategic Approach	10	0.49-.78	0.72	0.68
Neuroticism	08	0.62-.85	0.92	0.69
Extraversion	08	0.53-.83	0.90	0.71
Openness to experience	10	0.64-.51	0.86	0.71
Agreeableness	09	0.55-.70	0.77	0.70
Conscientiousness	09	0.51-.76	0.89	0.78

Sources : primary data collected by Author

For achieving the second objective of the pilot study, the feedback of the respondent was analyzed. They suggested rephrasing of some of the item and replacement of few words with easy to understand words.

3.5 Main Study

3.5.1 Research Questions of main Study

To achieve objective of the study following research questions are developed

Q1: What is overall personality orientation and student learning approaches preferences of all respondents?

Q2: How demographics are associated with student learning approaches?

Q3: How personality dimensions affect student learning approaches?

Getting support from literature presented and elaborated following hypothesis were formulated to answer research question three (RQ3)

- **H1a:** Extraversion will be positively associated with the deep learning approach.
- **H1b:** Extraversion will be positively associated with the strategic learning approach.
- **H2:** Neuroticism will be negatively associated with deep learning approach.
- **H3a:** Openness will be positively associated with the deep learning approach.
- **H3b:** Openness will be positively associated with the strategic learning approach.
- **H4a:** Conscientiousness will be positively associated with the deep learning approach.
- **H4b:** Conscientiousness will be positively associated with the strategic learning approach.
- **H5a:** Agreeableness will be positively associated with the deep learning approach.
- **H5b:** Agreeableness will be positively associated with the strategic learning approach.
- **H6:** Neuroticism will be positively associated with surface approach.
- **H7:** Openness to experiences will not be significantly associated with the surface learning approach.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 4.1 : Demographic Characteristics of respondents

Characteristic	Number and Percentage
Gender	
Male	114 (57%)
Female	86(43%)
Age	
20 – 25 years	102 (51%)
26 - 30 years	71(35.5%)
31 -35 years	16(8%)
36 and above years	11(5.5%)

The shows results	Program		Table the of
	Ms/MBA3.5	79(39.5%)	
	BBA(Hon)MBA1.5	61(30.5%)	
	Others	60(30%)	
	Prior education		
	B.com	42(21%)	
	BBA	60(30%)	
	Bsc/BA	48(24%)	
Other	50(25%)		

reliability and validity analyses of the questionnaire items. Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test of measuring sampling adequacy showed that it was acceptable. The values within ranges of 0.90 to 0.70 are generally acceptable (Kaiser, 1974). The Cronbach Alpha values are also above 0.70, which indicated that all items have good reliability. The statistical analyses for reliability and validity confirm that measurement scales have met the acceptable standard of reliability and validity.

The Table shows the descriptive statistics and correlations analysis and for eight variables. The means for each variable range from 3.0 to 3.7 showing that levels of personality dimension, extraversion, neuroticism, agreeableness, openness to experiences, conscientiousness, deep approach, strategic approach and surface approach range from moderately high to highest level. While the correlation coefficients values are less than 0.90, which indicated that the data have not affected by co-linearity problem serious (Hair et al., 2006). The relationship between extraversion and deep approach is positively and significant ($r = .580, p < 0.01$) and also positively significant relationship with strategic and surface approach with a value of ($r = .502, p < 0.01$ and $r = .281, p < 0.01$ respectively). The relationship between agreeableness and deep approach is positively and significant ($r = .673, p < 0.01$) and also positively significant relationship with strategic and surface approach with a value of ($r = .383, p < 0.01$ and $r = .480, p < 0.01$ respectively). The relationship between conscientiousness and deep approach is positively and significant ($r = .498, p < 0.01$) and also positively significant relationship with strategic and surface approach with a value of ($r = .184, p < 0.01$ and $r = .264, p < 0.01$ respectively). The relationship between neuroticism and deep approach is positively and significant ($r = .449, p < 0.01$) and also positively related with strategic approach significantly ($r = .161, p < 0.01$) while with surface approach there is no relation neuroticism. Moreover the personality traits and surface approach have positively significant with the value of ($r = .272, p < 0.01$). The relationship between openness to experiences and deep approach is positively and significant ($r = .703, p < 0.01$) and also positively significant relationship with strategic and surface approach with a value of ($r = .361, p < 0.01$ and $r = .432, p < 0.01$ respectively).

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	DELA	STLA	SULA	EXT	AGR	CON	NUR	OPE
DELA	3.3675	.78988	.549**	1						
STLA	3.3965	.75731	.518**	.600**	1					
SULA	3.1735	.73713	.272**	.442**	.359**	1				
EXT	3.4631	.68623	.580**	.502**	.281**	.146*	1			
AGR	3.5961	.73045	.673**	.383**	.480**	.201**	.267**	1		
CON	3.7050	.55277	.498**	.184**	.264**	-.071	.223**	.165*	1	
NUR	3.3075	.77753	.449**	.161	.053	.299**	-.038	.131	.026	1
OPE	3.3508	.79923	.703**	.361**	.432**	.155*	.287**	.364**	.235**	.088

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level DELA = Deep Approach, STLA = Strategic Approach, SULA = Surface Approach, EXT = Extraversion, AGR = Agreeableness, CON = Conscientiousness, NUR = Neuroticism, OPE = Openness

Table 4.4: Goodness of fit and values of indices in the model

Indices	Goodness of fit	Values
χ^2/df	2 -----> 5	1.371
CFI	>0.95	.98

TLI	>.0.95	.90
NFI	>.0.95	.98
RMSEA	0.5----->0.8	.063

Before deliberating hypotheses results projected by the research, the overall fit of structural model was assessed for evaluating the extent of proposed causal relationships between the latent constructs that fits the research data. It is recommended for a research to have one absolute fit index and one incremental index along with the Chi-square and the degrees of freedom value (Hair et al., 2010). GFI and RMSEA were reported as absolute fit indices, and CFI and TLI were reported as incremental fit indices. Hence, the overall fit of structural model was assessed with the same set of fit indices as those of measurement models. The fit indices indicated, the structural model to have a good fit with data (2/df = 1.37, CFI = 0.98, NFI = 0.98, TLI = 0.90, RMSEA = 0.063), thus supporting the basic theoretical framework of research. Thus, when all Big Five and learning approaches are simultaneously considered, only Openness to experiences and Conscientiousness have a significant effect on learning approaches (strategic approaches), negatively affecting Surface and positively affecting Deep learning (accounting for 67% of the variance in each factor).

Table 4.5: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
Strategicapproach	<---	Extraversion	.276	.073	3.780	***	Supported
Strategicapproach	<---	Agreeableness	.087	.077	1.131	.258	Not supported
Strategicapproach	<---	Conscientiousness	.034	.090	.377	.707	Not supported
Strategicapproach	<---	Neuroticism	.028	.072	.382	.702	Not supported
Strategicapproach	<---	Openness	.680	.076	8.982	***	supported
SurfaceApproach	<---	Agreeableness	.088	.098	.892	.373	Not supported
DeepApproach	<---	Agreeableness	-.023	.089	-.260	.795	Not supported
SurfaceApproach	<---	Conscientiousness	-.043	.122	-.352	.725	Not supported
DeepApproach	<---	Conscientiousness	-.020	.105	-.189	.850	Not supported
SurfaceApproach	<---	Neuroticism	.191	.098	1.961	.050	Not supported
DeepApproach	<---	Openness	.294	.090	3.282	.001	Not supported
SurfaceApproach	<---	Extraversion	.294	.094	3.112	.002	Not supported
DeepApproach	<---	Extraversion	.552	.084	6.610	***	supported

5. Results and Discussions

Result of this study found that business students enrolled in public and private sector universities of KPK (Pakistan) were high on conscientiousness ($M=3.70$, $SD=.55$) followed by agreeableness ($M=3.60$, $SD=.73$), extraversion ($M=3.46$, $SD=.69$), openness ($M=3.35$, $SD=.79$) and neuroticism ($M=3.31$, $SD=.78$). The mostly adopted students learning approach is strategic approach ($M=3.39$, $SD=.75$), then deep approach ($M=3.36$, $SD=.79$) and surface approach ($M=3.17$, $SD=.73$). The chi square revealed that gender has significant relations with deep approach ($\chi^2=4.18$, $df=32$, $p<0.050$) while have no significant relationship with strategic and surface.

While there is no significant relationship between learning approaches and age. Deep and strategic approaches have significant relationship with prior education ($\chi^2=127.556$, $df=96$, $p<0.05$ and $\chi^2=126$, $df=99$, $p<0.05$ respectively), and surface approach has no significant relationship with prior education. Our result showed that male are higher on deep approach ($M=3.502$, $SD=0.73$) than female ($M=3.19$, $SD=0.79$). These results are in line with (Duff, 1999, 2002; Tsang, 1998). But contradictory to their findings, our result showed that male ($M=3.2202$, $SD=0.647$) are higher on surface approach than females ($M=3.17$, $SD=0.737$). One of the possible reason behind this is that sample was taken from MS/MBA last/final semester students from management department.

While previous studies were based on undergraduate students under different disciplines. The difference of level and discipline may be the possible information for these contradictory results as Dasari (2006) argued that student adopted learning approaches also vary from discipline to discipline. In this study there is no significant relation of age with learning approaches which confirmed previous findings (Duff et al., 2004). Prior education is significantly correlated with deep and strategic approaches.

The primary purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between personality dimension and student learning approaches. This study found that four personality dimension for example extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience have positive correlation with deep, surface, strategic learning approaches. Only one dimension neuroticism did not significantly correlated with surface approach, while it has

positive and significant relationship with remaining two approaches, for example deep and strategic. These findings confirmed previous results (Busato et al., 1999, 2000; De Raad&Schouwenburg, 1996, Busato et al. 1999, Zhang 2003, Duff et al. 2004, Chamorro-Premuzic and Furnham 2008, Chamorro-Premuzic et al. 2007). The study also showed that all personality dimensions have impact on deep learning approach. Openness to experience is the only dimension that did not influence the surface approach while rest have impact on it. Neuroticism has no impact on strategic approach while other four dimensions have impact on strategic approach.

Our results contradicted some previous findings. For examples neuroticism has negative relationship with deep approach (Zhang, 2003; Duff et al, 2004; Bustao et al, 1999). These contradictions may be attributed to small sample size of this study, difference in cultural settings. The difference of level and discipline may be the possible explanation for these contradictory results as Dasari (2006) argued that students adopted learning approaches as vary from discipline to discipline.

5.1 Contribution of the study

It is the first ever study in Pakistan to explain relationship between personality and student learning approaches of business student. It also provides the information about the most adopted and the least adopted student learning approaches during their academic career. The most preferred student learning approach is strategic approach, and the least preferred approach is surface approach. This study helps in unearthing the high and low personality dimensions of business students. In this study the high dimensions of personality of student are having conscientiousness and low personality dimension have neuroticism. This study also confirmed previous findings

5.2 Implication of the Study

The knowledge, skills, and experiences that students bring from university to organization and the foundations laid in organization are often crucial to their future success. This means that teachers in today's education sector face a significant burden in not only conveying discipline content and practices but also setting path for the students on the path to becoming self-directed learners. The challenge is delivering a learning environment that is inclusive and caters for the increasing diversity among student populations. A middle of the road approach is no longer appropriate. Acknowledging diversity is one thing – achieving inclusiveness is another.

A key way for teachers to make effective adjustments to their curricula is to better understand exactly what factors make a difference between success and failure for individual students. Acknowledging that different individuals bring different learning approaches and backgrounds to the learning context is the first step in providing a more inclusive learning environment. What are the implications of these findings for research and education?" For research, the present findings suggest that the well-established five personality traits measure can be used to inform the learning approaches issue.

However, since the amount of variance explained by the personality traits in learning approaches is limited (between 15 and 67%), the personality inventory should not be used alone in the study of students' learning approaches. Since this is the first study of the predictive power of the five traits for learning approaches, replications of this study would certainly be valuable in verifying this predictive relationship. In educational settings, teachers may make use of the relationships between personality traits and learning approaches.

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